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Promoting Quality in Apprenticeships: Self-evaluation as an Instrument for Trainers to Assess Apprenticeship Quality

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Abstract

The article compares several in-company cases to study the relationship between the influence of the work environment on the quality of an apprenticeship. This in order to find out which kind of conditions of the work and learning environment have an positive influence on the quality of an apprenticeship. These conditions relate to a range of issues such as trainer performance, work task, infrastructure, support guidelines, frameworks. To get informed statements on the quality of training processes within the company learning environment the responsible trainers are interviewed. In the last chapter the cases are analysed to identify key lessons for an quality oriented apprenticeship.

Keywords

quality apprenticeships; innovative work environment; trainers; guidelines; self-evaluation

1 Introduction

There is increased interest in a deeper understanding of learning in apprenticeships. The reasons for this are twofold: on the one hand, dual vocational training and education receive much interest as a strong bridge between the education system and employment. On the other hand, some countries began to implement dual elements of apprenticeship like increasing time of internships or closer cooperation and coordination between vocational school or college and in-company apprenticeships. Crucial for these developments to succeed is to secure and develop quality.

To develop a quality model, one first has to choose relevant criteria and indicators underlining them. These criteria have to represent important aspects of quality in apprenticeships. Questions to be answered are: What are suitable criteria which reflect key functions of a good apprenticeship? How can relevant criteria be integrated and applied into apprenticeship quality assessment concepts? How can this be used as a quality improvement instrument for companies who train via apprenticeship? The article will compare several company cases in order to find out which criteria are key for quality of an apprenticeship as well as how the assessments can be used to promote high standards.

2 Methodological considerations of how to evaluate quality

To get informed statements on the quality of training and the learning processes involved, one has to ask the people that actually take part in these processes – trainers and apprentices. In this article, we draw mainly on the first group. In the last ten years, a web-based self-evaluation tool for trainers was developed and vocational teacher students carried out a vari-

ety of research projects in order to validate the tool's quantitative findings in a discourse involving key stakeholders as full time and part time trainers, company managers, and others in and outside the company.

The quality of learning within an apprenticeship is evaluated by questioning the trainers about six main criteria. The first four criteria and indicators are input criteria representing quality of the 'in-company work and learning processes'. The last two criteria (output dimensions) are related to the effect of the training on the apprentice's development in terms of professional competence as well as his or her commitment to the job.

The six main criteria are:

1. **Reflective Work Experience:** Experience-based learning in the work process is central for vocational training. Therefore the amount of time spent on learning in productive work processes can be used as an indicator for the quality of training.
2. **Professional Level of Training:** The higher the degree of complexity of work tasks, the more can be learned. Trainers are asked to what degree the assignments of the trainees or apprentices reach the level of 'professional tasks' (as opposed to 'everyman's simple tasks').
3. **Autonomous/independent learning:** This criterion investigates the relationship between detailed assignments and the apprentices' ability to perform tasks independently. Are the apprentices able to plan, do, act and control their work task on their own?
4. **Learning in business processes:** This criterion collects figures from the trainers about the degree to which the apprentices participated in real work assignments.
5. **Professional competence:** Indicators for a learner's fitness for occupation are the results of the final vocational examination, e.g. the number of attempts and the adjustment time needed after completion of the apprenticeship programme to reach the competence level of a skilled worker.
6. **Vocational commitment:** This criterion assesses the apprentices' commitment to the company and the professional occupation as well as the extent to which they accomplish their own work tasks independent

The article will compare nine apprenticeship cases in order to find which of the quality criteria are most relevant and influencing the quality development process. The quality, return and cost tool is based on 25 questions which offer the possibility to generate several graphical elements. This allows than to access the quality criteria and by which circumstances in each particular case the apprenticeship development has been of good or of less good quality. These judgements are based on the assessments undertaken by the full and part time trainers which are responsible for the apprenticeship arrangements in the company.

3 Reflection of several QRC cases

The article will show several cases from different sectors and occupations. The nine cases come from different labour market areas, such as industrial and craft trade sectors. Included here are professions such as industrial & building electricians, mechatronics technicians, mechanics, hairdressers and painters. All cases are analysed using the QRC tool. They were investigated to find out whether there is a relationship between the quality of the learning vironment and the innovative capability of the apprentices.

An overview of the cases will be shown via a Table (cannot printed here while too large), which covers company types, occupations concerned and the achieved QEK results: quality index and strength/weaknesses achieved. The different cases are ranked in three fields: *top, middle and lower field*. The first three represent stronger apprenticeships organised in such a way that they develop the innovative capabilities of apprentices. Three cases are clustered in the middle field.

All cases are above average but still have different weaknesses regarding some of the dimensions of the QEK tool (e.g. too little trainer support for apprentices, lack of a range of relevant occupational oriented work tasks, too many silly task for the apprentices). The cases in the lower area are below the common quality standards in the sectors. In all aspects of the QEK tool, they display greater or smaller deficits represented by weak quality indexes and 'poor' spiders. The comparisons are possible because they are taken out of a pool of more than 170 companies in several German regions (Rauner et.al. 2008).

The results from the assessments by the company trainers showed several problems and challenges in the apprenticeships: Too much work while too little learning: The cases show that it is important to build capacities on learning right from the beginning of an apprenticeship. This means that apprentices are best motivated by real *work and learning tasks*. Many companies miss a range of good practice examples: Work and learning tasks are integral parts of the company's business processes and they can increase in their difficulty and complexity: *from beginner to advanced beginner to professional tasks*. As shown in examples of good practice, this is done by maximising the learning time within the working time.

Are the apprentices' work tasks comprehensive with planning and preparation as well as control and documentation? Work tasks to train apprentices should follow a comprehensive work task structure. This means that the apprentice learns to do the practical job but also understands its relation to other activities such as planning the work, and preparing and assessing the results. This also covers feedback on the work activities. The product quality must be discussed to see whether the quality of the product can be met, or if not: Where are the difficulties and obstacles?

Work and Learning Task as a integral part of the company's business process: The work and learning tasks must be arranged in a systematic order, and not arbitrarily. For the trainer it is therefore important to consider which learning and work tasks are appropriate for the current status of the apprentice. In some company learning cases, it may be advisable for the trainer to plan a deeper investigation of his company. A questionnaire or an investigation grid

with the most important aspects could be used here. Such instruments turn a non-systematic visit by the trainer into a target-oriented investigation (Deitmer 2011).

The work task should force apprentices to cooperate with colleagues and other departments: The basic idea is to develop a range of working and learning task that match the practical skill needs of work tasks and which, although covering a complete task, build upon each other, and in total cover the complete business processes. Work task not only describe the object of the work, working methods, work instruments and other requirements, they should also include learning through others and in cooperation with others. (Howe et al. 2002)

In general, weaknesses regarding the quality of in-company training are linked to the following factors:

1. Low share of learning in real business processes
2. Low level of work tasks (degree of diversity)
3. Low orientation on work processes.

Such deficits find their expression in a low competence level of apprentices. But if the potentials of learning in qualifying work processes are maxed out, it is possible to:

4. Reach higher competence levels and to
5. Lower the costs of training.

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Biographical notes

Dr. Ludger Deitmer is as a senior fellow at ITB. He started as a VET teacher before he took part as a researcher in a range of regional, national and international pilot projects. New pathways for active learning processes were evaluated. His fields of interest are high qualitative and innovative VET approaches in companies and training centres and to study the changing expertise of VET trainers and apprentices. He is honorary member of the VET research network as part of the European Association of Educational Research (EERA).

Dr. Lars Heinemann works for almost 20 years as a Senior Researcher at the Institute Technology and Education (ITB) at Bremen University. His main areas of interest are development of occupational competence, vocational learning with new media and inclusion in vocational education.